

On the Approximate Solution of the Multi-Term Time-Fractional Diffusion Problem through Hermite Polynomials

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Abstract

This research presents a novel approach for constructing approximate solutions to multi-term time fractional diffusion problems through Hermite polynomials, the Residual Power Series Method (RPSM), and collocation techniques. Initially, the multi-term time fractional diffusion equation is transformed into a single-term equation using the Riemann integral, simplifying the original problem. Next, Hermite polynomials are employed to express the solution as a series, which, through the application of collocation points, reduces the problem to a system of fractional differential and algebraic equations. The RPSM is then applied to determine the unknown coefficient functions in the series representation. By substituting these coefficients back into the series, an approximate solution is constructed. To illustrate the applicability and accuracy of the proposed method, three numerical examples are provided, demonstrating its effectiveness in solving complex fractional diffusion problems.

Keywords: Multi-term time-fractional diffusion equation, Hermite Collocation method, Residual power series method.

1 Introduction

Fractional diffusion equations with various boundary conditions are widely used to analyze anomalous diffusion processes, such as super-diffusion and sub-diffusion. In particular, time-fractional diffusion equations have gained significant attention across multiple scientific disciplines, including mathematics, physics, biochemistry, finance, and medicine [1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8]. In the mathematical modeling of diffusion processes, fractional differential equations play a substantial role to analyze the processes in detail. These equations have a wide range of applications in various fields of science and engineering, as the order of the fractional derivative and Riemann integration could be any real number, such as $m - 1 \leq \alpha, \beta \leq m : m \in N$. As a result, fractional-order derivatives have been extensively studied and developed to interpret real-life phenomena such as biological systems, thermal conductivity, and chemical diffusion more accurately [9, 10, 11]. The

main concern of the current research is to establish approximate solutions to multi-term time fractional diffusion problem through a proposed method, a combination of Hermite polynomials, RPSM [12, 13, 14, 15, 16] and collocation method.

In this study, the following the multi-term time-fractional diffusion problem is considered:

$$D_t^\alpha u(x, t) + D_t^\beta u(x, t) = u_{xx}(x, t) + F(x, t, u), x \in (0, \ell), t \in (0, T) \quad (1)$$

subject to the initial and boundary conditions

$$u(x, 0) = \phi(x), x \in [0, \ell] \quad (2)$$

$$u(0, t) = \mu_1(t), t \in [0, T] \quad (3)$$

$$u(\ell, t) = \mu_2(t), t \in [0, T] \quad (4)$$

The organization of the rest of the paper is given as follows. In Section 2, related preliminaries of the problem are presented. Hermite polynomials and their properties are given in Section 3. In Section 4, the algorithms of the developed methods are presented. Some examples are demonstrated to verify the advantages of the proposed methods in Section 5. Finally, a brief conclusion is presented to summarize the outcomes in Section 6.

2 Preliminaries

In this section, fundamental definitions and notions are presented.

Definition 2.1. The Riemann-Liouville integral for α is [17, 18, 19, 20]:

$$J^\alpha f(x) = \begin{cases} \frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha)} \int_0^x (x - \tau)^{\alpha-1} f(\tau) d\tau, & \alpha > 0 \\ f(x) & , \alpha = 0. \end{cases} \quad (5)$$

Definition 2.2. The α^{th} order fractional derivative in Caputo sense is given by [17, 18, 19]:

$$D^\alpha f(x) = J^{m-\alpha}(D^m f(x)) = \begin{cases} \frac{1}{\Gamma(m-\alpha)} \int_0^x (x - \tau)^{m-\alpha-1} f^{(m)}(\tau) d\tau, & m - 1 < \alpha < m, m \in N, \\ \frac{d^{(m)}}{dx^{(m)}} f(x) & , \alpha = m. \end{cases} \quad (6)$$

which has the following properties:

- $D^\alpha C = 0$, (C is a constant)
- $D^\alpha J^\alpha f(x) = f(x)$,

- $J^\alpha D^\alpha f(x) = f(x) - \sum_{i=0}^{m-1} f^{(i)}(0) \frac{x^i}{\Gamma(i+1)},$

-

$$J^\beta(D^\alpha f(x)) = \begin{cases} D^{\alpha-\beta} f(x) - \frac{t^{\beta-\alpha}}{\Gamma(\beta+1-\alpha)} f(0), & \alpha < \beta \\ J^{\beta+1-\alpha} f'(x), & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases} \quad (7)$$

Definition 2.3. A power series expansion of the form

$$\sum_{n=0}^{\infty} c_n (t - t_0)^{n\alpha} = c_0 + c_1 (t - t_0)^\alpha + c_2 (t - t_0)^{2\alpha} + \dots, \quad (8)$$

$$0 \leq m - 1 < \alpha \leq m, \quad t \geq t_0$$

is called fractional power series about $t = t_0$ [19].

Theorem 2.1. Suppose that f has a fractional power series representation at t_0 of the form

$$f(t) = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} c_n (t - t_0)^{n\alpha}, \quad 0 \leq m - 1 < \alpha \leq 1, \quad t_0 \leq t < t_0 + R. \quad (9)$$

If $f(t) \in C[t_0, t_0 + R]$ and $D_{t_0}^{n\alpha} f(t) \in C(t_0, t_0 + R)$ for $n = 0, 1, 2, \dots$, then the coefficients c_n in Eq. (10) will take the form of

$$c_n = \frac{D_{t_0}^{n\alpha} f(t_0)}{\Gamma(1 + n\alpha)}, \quad (10)$$

where $D_{t_0}^{n\alpha} = D_{t_0}^\alpha D_{t_0}^\alpha \dots D_{t_0}^\alpha$ (n times) [19].

3 Hermite polynomials (HP)

Hermite polynomials $H_n, n \in N$ are the solutions of the following differential equations [21, 22, 23]:

$$H_{n+1}(x) + H_n'(x) - 2xH_n(x) = 0, \quad H_n'(x) = 2nH_{n-1}(x) \quad (11)$$

which can be represented in the series form as follows:

$$H_n(x) = \Gamma(n+1) \sum_{k=0}^{[n/2]} \frac{(-1)^k (2x)^{n-2k}}{2^k \Gamma(k+1) \Gamma(n-2k+1)}, \quad n \in N_0 \quad (12)$$

Moreover, the recursion formula for Hermite polynomials are presented as:

$$\begin{aligned} H_0(x) &\equiv 1, \quad H_1(x) = 2x, \\ H_{n+1}(x) &= 2xH_n(x) - 2nH_{n-1}(x), \quad n \geq 1, \end{aligned} \quad (13)$$

A significant property of Hermite polynomials is that they form an orthogonal system in $L_2(R, w)$:

$$\int_{-\infty}^{\infty} H_n(x)H_m(x)\omega(x)dx = \sqrt{2\pi}2^n\Gamma(n+1)\delta_{nm} \quad (14)$$

where $\omega(x) = \exp(-x^2)$ and δ_{nm} is the Kronecker delta. Hence one can obtain a system of orthonormal Hermite polynomials $\psi_n(x), n = 1, 2, \dots$

$$\int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \psi_n(x)\psi_m(x)\omega(x)dx = \delta_{nm}. \quad (15)$$

Since Hermite polynomials are smooth functions, the solution can be interpolated and the problem transformed into an algebraic system of equations which is easily handled by computational software such as MATLAB and many others.

4 Algorithmic Framework and Implementation of the Proposed Method

In order to reduce multi-term time fractional diffusion problem into a single term time fractional diffusion problem, Riemann integral of order β is applied to the fractional differential equation :

$$D_t^\alpha u(x, t) + D_t^\beta u(x, t) = u_{xx}(x, t) + F(x, t, u), \quad (16)$$

which yields the following

$$D_t^{\alpha-\beta} u(x, t) = J_t^\beta u_{xx}(x, t) + u(x, 0) \left(1 + \frac{t^{\beta-\alpha}}{\Gamma(\beta+1-\alpha)}\right) - u(x, t) + J_t^\beta F(x, t, u). \quad (17)$$

At this stage, the steps of the algorithm for the method can be listed as:

Step 1. We assume that $u(x, t)$ is sufficiently smooth functions to be approximated by truncating the series in terms of Hermite polynomials as follows:

$$u(x, t) \approx \sum_{n=0}^{M-1} c_n(t)H_n(x), \quad (18)$$

Step 2. Plugging the M^{th} degree approximation of Eq.(18) into the Eq.(17) yields the following:

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{n=0}^{M-1} D_t^{\alpha-\beta} c_n(t)H_n(x) &= \sum_{n=0}^{M-1} J_t^\beta c_n(t)H_n''(x) + \sum_{n=0}^{M-1} c_n(0)H_n(x) \left(1 + \frac{t^{\beta-\alpha}}{\Gamma(\beta+1-\alpha)}\right) \\ &\quad - \sum_{n=0}^{M-1} c_n(t)H_n(x) + J_t^\beta F\left(x, t, \sum_{n=0}^{M-1} c_n(t)H_n(x)\right), \end{aligned} \quad (19)$$

Step 3. Employing the collocation points at $x_r = \frac{2j-1}{M}, j = 1, 2, \dots, M - 1$ leads to the following system of fractional ordinary differential equations:

$$\sum_{n=0}^{M-1} D_t^{\alpha-\beta} c_n(t) H_n(x_r) = \sum_{n=0}^{M-1} J_t^\beta c_n(t) H_n''(x_r) + \sum_{n=0}^{M-1} c_n(0) H_n(x_r) \left(1 + \frac{t^{\beta-\alpha}}{\Gamma(\beta+1-\alpha)}\right) - \sum_{n=0}^{M-1} c_n(t) H_n(x_r) + J_t^\beta F\left(x_r, t, \sum_{n=0}^{M-1} c_n(t) H_n(x_r)\right), \quad (20)$$

Step 4. Initial and boundary conditions Eq.(2)-(4) in the reduced problem give rise to the following system of $(M + 1)$ algebraic equations :

$$\sum_{n=0}^{M-1} c_n(0) H_n(x_r) = \phi(x_r) \quad (21)$$

$$\sum_{n=0}^{M-1} c_n(t) H_n(0) = \mu_1(t) \quad (22)$$

$$\sum_{n=0}^{M-1} c_n(t) H_n(1) = \mu_2(t) \quad (23)$$

which allows us to determine the initial values of coefficients for $c_n(t), n = 0, 1, \dots, M - 1$ in the series representation of the solution .

Step 5. The utilization of RPSM leads to establish the unknown functions $c_n(t), n = 0, 1, \dots, M - 1$. Moreover, placing the obtained coefficient functions $c_n(t), n = 0, 1, \dots, M - 1$ back into the series leads to approximate solution $u_M(x, t)$.

5 Illustrative Examples

This section provides three examples to confirm the accuracy and effectiveness of the proposed method as well as its implementation.

Example 1. Consider the multi-term time-fractional diffusion equation

$$D_t^\alpha u(x, t) + D_t^\beta u(x, t) = u_{xx}(x, t) + F(x, t), 0 < \beta < \alpha < 1, x \in (0, 1), t \in (0, 1) \quad (24)$$

subject to the initial and boundary conditions

$$u(x, 0) = 0, x \in [0, 1] \quad (25)$$

$$u(0, t) = u(1, t) = 0, t \in [0, 1] \quad (26)$$

where $F(x, t) = \Gamma(1 + 2\alpha - 2\beta) \left(\frac{t^{\alpha-2\beta}}{\Gamma(1+\alpha-2\beta)} + \frac{t^{2\alpha-3\beta}}{\Gamma(1+2\alpha-3\beta)} \right) x(1-x) + 2t^{2\alpha-2\beta}$. The analytical solution of the considered problem is obtained as $u(x, t) = x(1-x)t^{2\alpha-2\beta}$.

In Fig. 1, the graphs of exact and approximate solutions of $u(x, t)$ at $t = 0.8$ for various values of α, β and $m = 3$ are presented. In Fig 2., the 3D graphs of absolute errors for $\alpha = 0.9, \beta = 0.4$ and $m = 3$ are given. In Table 1., the exact solution and absolute errors for various values of

Figure 1: The graphs of exact and approximate solutions of $u(x, t)$ for various values of α, β of Ex.1 .

Figure 2: The 3D graphs of absolute errors for $\alpha = 0.9, \beta = 0.4$ of Ex.1.

x, t with $m = 3$ at $\alpha = 0.9, \beta = 0.4$ are presented. *Example 2.* Consider the multi-term time-fractional diffusion equation

$$D_t^\alpha u(x, t) + D_t^\beta u(x, t) = u_{xx}(x, t) + u(x, t) + F(x, t), 0 < \beta < \alpha < 1, x \in (0, 1), t \in (0, 1) \quad (27)$$

subject to the initial and boundary conditions

$$u(x, 0) = 0, x \in [0, 1] \quad (28)$$

$$u(0, t) = t^{2\alpha-2\beta} - t^{\alpha-\beta}, t \in [0, 1] \quad (29)$$

$$u(1, t) = 4(t^{2\alpha-2\beta} - t^{\alpha-\beta}), t \in [0, 1] \quad (30)$$

Table 1: The values of absolute errors for $m = 3$ and $\alpha = 0.9, \beta = 0.4$ of Ex. 1.

x/t	0.1	0.3	0.5	0.7	0.9
0.1	0	6.9389e-18	2.0817e-17	0	0
0.3	0	0	2.7756e-17	2.7756e-17	2.7756e-17
0.5	6.9389e-18	1.3878e-17	0	5.5511e-17	2.7756e-17
0.7	1.3878e-17	2.7756e-17	2.7756e-17	2.7756e-17	2.7756e-17
0.9	1.7347e-18	3.4694e-18	6.9389e-18	1.3878e-17	8.3267e-17

Figure 3: The graphs of exact and approximate solutions of $u(x, t)$ of Ex.1 .

Figure 4: The 3D graphs of absolute errors for $\alpha = 0.9, \beta = 0.4$ of Ex.1.

where $F(x, t) = (3x^3 + 1) \left(\Gamma(1 + 2\alpha - 2\beta) \frac{t^{\alpha - 2\beta}}{\Gamma(1 + \alpha - 2\beta)} - \Gamma(1 + \alpha - \beta) \frac{t^{-\beta}}{\Gamma(1 - \beta)} + \Gamma(1 + 2\alpha - 2\beta) \frac{t^{2\alpha - 3\beta}}{\Gamma(1 + 2\alpha - 3\beta)} - \Gamma(1 + \alpha - \beta) \frac{t^{\alpha - 2\beta}}{\Gamma(1 + \alpha - 2\beta)} \right) - (3x^3 + 18x + 1)(t^{2\alpha - 2\beta} - t^{\alpha - \beta})$. The analytical solution of the considered problem is obtained $u(x, t) = (3x^3 + 1)(t^{2\alpha - 2\beta} - t^{\alpha - \beta})$.

In Fig. 3, the graphs of exact and approximate solutions of $u(x, t)$ at $t = 0.8$ for various values of α, β and $m = 4$ are presented. In Fig 4., the 3D graphs of absolute errors for $\alpha = 0.9, \beta = 0.4$ and $m = 4$ are given. In Table 2., the exact solution and absolute errors for various values of x, t with $m = 4$ at $\alpha = 0.9, \beta = 0.4$ are presented.

Example 3. Consider the multi-term time-fractional diffusion equation

$$D_t^\alpha u(x, t) + D_t^\beta u(x, t) = u_{xx}(x, t) + xu_x(x, t) + F(x, t), 0 < \beta < \alpha < 1, x \in (0, 1), t \in (0, 1) \quad (31)$$

subject to the initial and boundary conditions

$$u(x, 0) = \cos(x), x \in [0, 1] \quad (32)$$

Table 2: The values of absolute errors for $m = 4$ at $t = 0.8$ and $\alpha = 0.9, \beta = 0.4$ of Ex. 1.

x/t	0.1	0.3	0.5	0.7
0.1	5.5511e-17	0	2.7756e-17	2.7756e-17
0.3	2.7756e-17	0	8.3267e-17	8.3267e-17
0.5	5.5511e-17	5.5511e-17	0	1.9429e-16
0.7	1.6653e-16	1.1102e-16	5.5511e-17	2.2204e-16
0.9	1.1102e-16	1.1102e-16	0	2.2204e-16

Figure 5: The graphs of exact and approximate solutions of $u(x, t)$ of Ex.1 .

Figure 6: The 3D graphs of absolute errors for $\alpha = 0.9, \beta = 0.4$ of Ex.1.

$$u(0, t) = t^{\alpha-\beta} + 1, t \in [0, 1] \tag{33}$$

$$u(1, t) = (t^{\alpha-\beta} + 1)\cos(1), t \in [0, 1] \tag{34}$$

where $F(x, t) = \cos(x)\left(\Gamma(1 + \alpha - \beta)\left(\frac{t^{-\beta}}{\Gamma(1-\beta)} + \frac{t^{\alpha-2\beta}}{\Gamma(1+\alpha-2\beta)}\right) + \left(\frac{t^{-\alpha}}{\Gamma(1-\alpha)} + \frac{t^{-\beta}}{\Gamma(1-\beta)}\right)\right) + (\cos(x) + x\sin(x))(t^{\alpha-\beta} + 1)$. The analytical solution of the considered problem is obtained $u(x, t) = \cos(x)(t^{\alpha-\beta} + 1)$.

In Fig. 5, the graphs of exact and approximate solutions of $u(x, t)$ at $t = 0.8$ for various values of α, β and $m = 8$ are presented. In Fig 6., the 3D graphs of absolute errors for $\alpha = 0.9, \beta = 0.4$ and $m = 8$ are given. In Table 3., the exact solution and absolute errors for various values of x, t with $m = 8$ at $\alpha = 0.9, \beta = 0.4$ are presented.

Table 3: The values of absolute errors for $m = 7$ at $t = 0.8$ and $\alpha = 0.9, \beta = 0.4$ of Ex. 1.

x/t	0	0.2	0.4	0.6	0.8	1
0	1.8974e-19	4.9031e-17	1.5244e-16	5.8382e-17	9.8251e-17	4.0146e-17
0.2	2.4769e-10	3.5425e-10	3.9839e-10	4.3226e-10	4.6081e-10	4.8596e-10
0.4	5.3825e-10	7.8255e-10	8.8374e-10	9.6138e-10	1.0268e-09	1.0845e-09
0.6	5.6719e-10	8.2117e-10	9.2637e-10	1.0071e-09	1.0752e-09	1.1351e-09
0.8	1.7391e-10	2.5385e-10	2.8697e-10	3.1237e-10	3.3379e-10	3.5267e-10
1	1.0391e-16	1.4621e-16	8.3338e-18	1.9409e-17	1.8851e-16	1.4425e-16

6 Conclusion

The main contribution of this work is the development of a novel approach for solving multi-term time fractional diffusion problems using the Riemann integral, Hermite polynomials, the Residual Power Series Method (RPSM), and collocation techniques. This method enables the construction of approximate solutions for a wide range of multi-term fractional problems. The core idea is to reduce the original multi-term fractional problem to a single-term fractional problem via the Riemann integral. Subsequently, Hermite polynomials, in conjunction with collocation points and RPSM, are employed to derive an approximate solution. Furthermore, Hermite polynomials can be replaced with other special polynomial families to potentially improve the accuracy of the solution, making the proposed method highly adaptable and versatile for tackling various multi-term fractional problems.

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